

EXERCISE OF ROAD TRANSPORT INCIDENTS IMPROVING TRANSMISSION PROCEDURES

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Abstract; Har one a person intended to the address arrived take for to the road get out it is his for security and comfortable a must to the circumstances have has been road through to go movement does if movement on time any one obstacle or vehicles risk put present in the day simple case being left Here it is so situations prevention get for xar one road traffic accident sure by doing organic exit need. Such cases of the vehicle to us and walk the body in the part residual traces to help will come.

Population lives in places the most a lot spread out from traffic accidents one at intersections collision and pedestrians pressing leave At the crossroads of the driver one of time in itself one how many vehicles and pedestrians group movement to evaluate right will come. Some at intersections view limited because of new appear vehicles with and another obstacles on time not understanding can Dimensions limited at intersections large trucks and of buses movement difficult will be

Key words; expertise, autotech, object, subject, expert, mechanism;

Analysis and results; Auto technician of expertise the subject of the vehicle technical situation, an accident occurred has been in place road movement status of the participants of the accident actions and their possibilities about real data, that's it including accident individual versions of participants; auto technician expert by their special knowledge and citizenship or arbitration of work materials as well administrative materials based on determined unhappy event mechanism as well crime happen to do help giving circumstances.

Auto technician of expertise common **objects:** vehicles (their parts, aggregates, mechanisms, systems, fragments), road, accident place, in them the rest tracks, driver, legal price Demand who does not crime work materials.

General characteristics with one in line automotive engineering expertise each one of type objects a little display can

Car expertise to himself special engineering and transportation expertise as subject, objects, tasks, used certain methods and in the literature difference doer species and small to species is divided. Auto technician in expertise to prove subject and special of knowledge content account received without the following species separate can:

- - event happen has been case studies;
- - of the vehicle technical study the situation;
- - in a vehicle traces and event happen has been place (transport- trasological diagnostics), as well as road technical situation, event happen has been in the place road study the situation;
- - repair value and residual value determination in order to study the vehicle.

This kind of automotive engineering expertise each one known one tasks to the circle have being them this kind of the examination independent respectively or another auto technician the examination types with together or to a transport class depends didn't happen the examination with solution to do possible - observation, medical the examination., materials, substances and of products forensic expertise, metallurgy, biological and others

Auto technician of expertise the subject of the vehicle technical situation, event happen has been in place road situation, accident of participants actions and their opportunities showing real direction data, that's it including automotive engineering individual versions of the test. accident participants, car accident mechanism, this the crime happen to do help giving circumstances account received without, expert - auto technician by this in the field to himself special special knowledge and materials based on is determined. citizenship or arbitration work as well administrative in character materials.

Automotive engineering expertise common attention in the center objects: vehicles (their structural parts, parts, systems, mechanisms and fragments), event happen the place, the way, the rest tracks, driver, crime work with directly depends has been materials. legal evaluation.

Automotive engineering direction check to himself special engineering and transportation expertise as one of time in itself this in progress used objects, topics, tasks, specific methods and in the literature difference doer a small species and to species is divided.

Auto technician expertise appointment unhappy of the event all criminal in their work is mandatory. Citizenship works according to court by forensic autotechnics expertise appointment, that's it including process of the participant at your request according to, unhappy of the event all cases, but the first next, uncertain and controversial circumstances determination for mandatory is considered Of this for, in particular, the following studies take going:

- unhappy event mechanism check
- unhappy event of participants actions check
- road movement of the rules violation check

The event happen has been of circumstances auto technician expertise of the event the guilty not to determine separately attention to give need - this investigation and court by of evidence generality based on done is increased. That's why for, of the article in the title The " finding " of guilt is a quote in. But auto engineering research to us how road movement the rules break and who by happen done, they event happen to be and It is also known to go of consequences to the beginning how effect that he did to determine possibility will give.

Certain traffic situation in learning auto technician of expertise the subject of vehicles status (from this since referred to as TS in the text), of a traffic accident mechanism (from this since in the text unhappy is called an event), an event in place road movement status and of drivers actions, as well as a car accident reason has been circumstances about real data they are expert technician by criminal (civil) case knowledge and materials.

Court automotive engineering expertise Russia Justice of the ministry court automotive engineering in the field special to knowledge have was, court automotive engineering expertise known in one specialty trained and court automotive engineering expertise independent work release the right received experts by done is increased.

Current at the time Center employees by the following kind of automotive engineering expertise held:

1. Traffic accident study of cases;
2. Vehicle in the means and traffic accident happen has been in the place study of traces transport- trasological diagnosis);
3. Vehicles their value and replacement value determination learning in order to repair.
4. Roads technical situation, traffic accident in place road study the conditions.

Figure 1. Traffic accident in place of the bus location mark

Figure 2. Road traffic accident in the scheme complicated configurable objects again Create.

Conclusion and Suggestions; The way cut transition rules complicated and done increase difficult that it was because of unhappy events happen it won't be. The majority offenders the rules they knew, but them broke Of course, the rules don't know or bad there are those who know. That's why for, again one there is road movement in the rules in the eye caught of pedestrians some main obligations remind I want to pass:

1. Pedestrians sidewalks or pedestrians corridors across, they no when while road edges across movement need Pedestrians, pedestrians corridors or road edges if not, as well they are across of movement possible didn't happen in the case of pedestrians bicycle the way across movement or commute part of at the edge (separable linear on roads - road across) one in line walking can commute part of external edge).
2. of the road commute part of from the edge while moving, pedestrian vehicles to the movement looking walks need Without engine disabled people in his carriage moving,

motorcycle, moped, bicycle leading persons such of vehicles in cases movement direction compliance to do required (age 14 incomplete to individuals common in use on the way bicycle to drive permission is given, but from the age small it's not). 16 years old moped driving for).

3. Pedestrians commute part pedestrians transition in places, that's it including husband under and tall transition in places, they no when and pedestrians corridors or road edges across at intersections cut transitions need View in the zone intersection or intersection if not, har two in the direction too obvious apparently standing separator line and barriers didn't happen in places the way commute part of to the edge right corner under cut to pass permission is given

In order not placed pedestrians transition in places pedestrians approaching coming transport to the means has been the distance, their speed from the calculation after and transition place they are for safe to be trust harvest from doing then, commuting to the part inputs can

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